

STUDY OF CLIMATIC VARIABILITY AT AKOLA STATION

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Abstract

Climate change is global problem. It has location specific effects. In this study annual and weekly climate variability in terms of rainfall, minimum and maximum temperature were analyzed for the period from 1998 to 2019 for Akola station. The increase in average annual maximum and minimum temperature for Akola station was found as 0.8% and 1.5%, respectively. The average reduction in annual rainfall for Akola station was 99.02 mm (11.76%) over the period of study.

Keywords: Climate change, rainfall, maximum temperature, minimum temperature.

Introduction

Crop growth is function of soil, water and climate. Agriculture production is influenced mostly by temperature and precipitation. Crops are sensitive to climate variability and weather extremes of droughts, floods and severe storms. Climate change is projected to affect agriculture and net outcome could be harmful or beneficial.

Rainfall is not uniform throughout the season. Water is the major limiting factor for crop diversification and production. Reductions in water availability for irrigation use increases the importance of implementation of water conservation practices in agriculture. Optimizing water use is an economic and environmental concern for agricultural producers.

Rainfall amounts and distribution are usually suboptimal in the district which often creates moisture-stress periods during one or more stages of crop growth, causing very low crop yields. Variation in rainfall amounts and distribution from one year to another causes substantial fluctuations in production. Climate change scenario is affecting the yield adversely. Thus, a study was carried out for accessing the climate variation at Akola station.

Material And Methods**2.1 Details of study area**

Akola district is one of the eleven districts of Vidarbha Region of Maharashtra state. It comes under subtropical zone. It is situated at an altitude of 307.415m above mean sea level at the intersection of 20° 42' North latitude and 77° 02' East longitude. Average annual precipitation of Akola is 760 mm.

Table 3.1 Variation in average climatic parameters at Akola station

Particulars	Period		Variation, mm	Variation, %
	1998-2008	2009-2019		
Average Annual Rainfall, mm	772.96	747.54	- 25.43	- 3.29
Maximum temperature, °C				
Minimum temperature, °C				

The increase in average annual maximum and minimum temperature for Akola station was found as 0.8% and 1.5%, respectively. The average reduction in annual rainfall for Akola station was 25.43 mm i.e., (3.29%). Fig 3.1 clears that the annual average rainfall reduced during 2009-

Fig. 3.1 Variation in average annual climatic parameters

2019 as compared to that during 1998 to 2008, while minimum and maximum temperature shows slightly increasing trend during 2009-2019 as compared to that during 1998 to 2008.

3.1.2 Weekly Climate Variation

The variation in average weekly maximum, minimum temperature along with average rainfall between two subseries i.e., 1998 to 2008

2.2 Data Collection

The daily rainfall data of Akola station was collected from www.maharain.gov.in. while maximum and minimum temperature data was collected from All India Coordinated Research Projects on Agrometeorology, Dr. PDKV Akola for period of 22 years i.e. 1998 to 2019.

2.3 Effect of climate change on rainfall and temperature

Daily rainfall, minimum and maximum temperature data for 22 years i.e. from 1998 to 2019 was used to find out the weekly climate variability. Linear trend method is the most significant technique to evaluate and analyse the short or long-term change of rainfall and temperature to assess climate change. The independent (time) and dependent (rainfall or temperature) variables are important variables. The annual and weekly rainfall minimum and maximum temperature were analysed for trend for the period from 1998 to 2019. The data was split into two groups each of eleven years for analysis purpose. The average annual rainfall, minimum and maximum temperature were plotted against year to study the climate variability.

Results And Discussion**Climatic Variability****Annual Climate Variability**

Annual climate variability in terms of temperature and rainfall was analysed. The analysed annual rainfall, minimum and maximum temperatures trend for period from 1998 to 2019 are presented in Table 3.1 and depicted in Fig. 3.1.

and 2009 to 2019 for SMW 23 to SMW 39 at Akola station is presented in Table 3.2 and depicted in Fig 3.2.

The highest reduction in average weekly maximum temperature observed for SMW 30 followed by 35, 23, 28, 31 and 29. The reduction in average weekly maximum temperature was 4.02%, 1.29%, 1.10%, 1.09%, 0.86% and 0.59% for SMW 30, 35, 23, 28, 31

and 29, respectively. The highest accretion in average weekly maximum temperature observed for SMW 24 followed by SMW 33, 26, 38, 26, 38, 25, 37, 39, 32, 27, 36 and 34. The accretion in average weekly maximum temperature was 3.58%, 3.09%, 2.53%, 2.14%, 2.05%, 1.94%, 1.89%, 1.71%, 0.97%, 0.87% and 0.65% for SMW 24, 33, 26, 38, 26, 38, 25, 37, 39, 32, 27, 36 and 34, respectively. The highest accretion in average weekly maximum temperature observed for June followed by September and August was 1.76%, 1.71% and 0.66%, respectively. Whereas reduction in average weekly maximum temperature observed for July was 1.18%. The average increase in average weekly maximum temperature for Akola station was 0.24°C (0.74%).

The highest reduction in average weekly minimum temperature observed for SMW 30 followed by SMW 34, 39, 31, 28, 38, 27, 36, and 25. The reduction in average weekly minimum temperature was 2.19%, 2.09%, 1.75%, 1.69%, 0.84%, 0.43%, 0.34%, 0.24% and 0.21% for SMW 30, 34, 39, 31, 28, 38, 27, 36, and 25, respectively. The highest accretion in average weekly minimum temperature observed for SMW 37 followed by SMW 24, 23, 35, 26, 29, 33 and 32. The accretion in average weekly minimum temperature was

1.40%, 1.04%, 1.03%, 0.37%, 0.24%, 0.17%, 0.04% and 0.03% for SMW 37, 24, 23, 35, 26, 29, 33 and 32, respectively. The highest reduction in average weekly minimum temperature observed for July followed by August and September was 0.80%, 0.67% and 0.26%, respectively. Whereas accretion in average weekly minimum temperature observed for June was 0.53%. The average reduction in average weekly minimum temperature for Akola station was 0.07°C (0.30%).

The reduction in average weekly rainfall was 66.40%, 43.49%, 34.26%, 24.99%, 20.94%, 16.95%, 16.36%, 13.35%, 12.10% and 4.57% for SMW 32, 39, 26, 37, 24, 29, 31, 25, 36 and SMW 23 respectively. The highest accretion in average weekly rainfall observed for SMW 28 followed by SMW 35, 30, 33, 38, 27 and 34. The accretion in weekly rainfall was 42.72%, 40.56%, 26.87%, 12.86%, 9.82%, 8.17%, 7.32% for SMW 28, 35, 30, 33, 38, 27 and SMW 34, respectively. The highest reduction in monthly rainfall observed for June, September and July was 18.28%, 17.69% and 4.40%, respectively. Whereas increase in average monthly rainfall observed in July was 15.20%. The average reduction in average weekly rainfall for Akola station was 4.26 mm/week (6.29%).

i) SMW 23

ii) SMW 24

iii) SMW 25

iv) SMW 26

v) SMW 27

vi) SMW 28

Table 3.2 Variation in average weekly maximum, minimum temperature and rainfall at Akola station

Month	SMW	Average Weekly Maximum Temperature, °c					Average Weekly Minimum Temperature, °c					Average Weekly Rainfall, mm				
		1998-2008	2009-2019	Variation,			1998-2008	2009-2019	Variation,			1998-2008	2009-2019	Variation,		
				°c	%	Monthly %			°c	°c	Monthly %			mm	%	Monthly %
Jun	23	39.62	39.19	-0.44	-1.10	1.76	26.82	27.10	0.28	1.03	0.53	18.17	17.34	-0.83	-4.57	-18.28
	24	36.17	37.47	1.29	3.58		25.64	25.91	0.27	1.04		54.35	42.97	-11.38	-20.94	
	25	34.63	35.34	0.71	2.05		25.26	25.21	-0.05	-0.21		38.21	33.11	-5.10	-13.35	
	26	33.28	34.12	0.84	2.53		24.66	24.72	0.06	0.24		57.04	37.49	-19.54	-34.26	
Jul	27	32.55	32.87	0.32	0.97	-1.18	24.26	24.18	-0.08	-0.34	-0.80	46.21	49.99	3.78	8.17	15.20
	28	32.12	31.77	-0.35	-1.09		24.29	24.08	-0.21	-0.84		35.81	51.10	15.30	42.72	
	29	31.24	31.06	-0.18	-0.59		23.92	23.96	0.04	0.17		49.20	40.86	-8.34	-16.95	
	30	30.76	29.52	-1.24	-4.02		23.49	22.98	-0.51	-2.19		59.50	75.49	15.99	26.87	
Aug	31	30.60	30.34	-0.26	-0.86	0.66	23.51	23.11	-0.40	-1.69	-0.67	67.19	56.20	-10.99	-16.36	-4.40
	32	29.29	29.79	0.50	1.71		23.27	23.28	0.01	0.03		78.83	26.49	-52.34	-66.40	
	33	30.08	31.01	0.93	3.09		23.28	23.29	0.01	0.04		23.36	26.36	3.01	12.86	
	34	30.20	30.39	0.20	0.65		23.25	22.77	-0.49	-2.09		40.54	43.51	2.97	7.32	
	35	30.75	30.35	-0.40	-1.29		22.89	22.98	0.09	0.37		31.64	44.47	12.83	40.56	
Sept	36	30.52	30.78	0.26	0.87	1.71	22.82	22.76	-0.06	-0.24	-0.26	44.61	39.21	-5.40	-12.10	-17.69
	37	31.24	31.85	0.61	1.94		22.60	22.92	0.32	1.40		30.37	22.78	-7.59	-24.99	
	38	31.10	31.77	0.66	2.14		22.72	22.62	-0.10	-0.43		32.66	35.87	3.21	9.82	
	39	32.34	32.95	0.61	1.89		22.63	22.23	-0.40	-1.75		18.38	10.39	-7.99	-43.49	
Avg				0.24		0.74			-0.07		-0.30			-4.26		-6.29

Fig. 3.2 Variation in average weekly climatic parameters for SMW 23 to SMW 39

Conclusion

Annual and weekly climate variability in terms of temperature and rainfall was studied for all talukas of Akola district. Average annual rainfall was reduced for all seven stations of Akola district. The increase in average annual maximum and minimum temperature for all stations in Akola was found as 0.8% and 1.5%, respectively. The average reduction in annual rainfall for Akola district was 99.02 mm (11.76%). The average weekly maximum temperature was increased by 0.74% whereas average weekly rainfall and average weekly minimum temperature was reduced by 6.29% and 0.3%, respectively during SMW 23 to SMW 39 in Akola district.

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